

RespInPeace: Toolkit for Processing Respiratory Belt Data

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Abstract

RespInPeace is a Python toolkit for processing respiratory data collected using Respiratory Inductance Plethysmography (RIP). It provides methods for signal normalisation, calibration, parametrisation as well as for detection of respiratory events, such as inhalations, exhalations and breath holds. The paper gives a short overview of the most important functions of the program.

Introduction

Respiratory Inductance Plethysmography (RIP, Watson, 1980) is one of the most common ways of recording kinematics of respiratory movements in humans (for an overview of respiratory measurement methods, see Primiano Jr., 2009). The method uses two elastic belts worn around the rib cage (above or below pectoral muscles) and the abdomen (at the level of the navel). As the belts stretch and contract due to respiratory activity, thin coils sewn into them generate changes in inductance linear to the changes of the upper body circumference. Assuming that the respiratory system has only two degrees of freedom, the summed signal can be used as a measure of relative lung volume change provided that sensitivity of individual belts is adjusted, for instance by performing the isovolume maneuver (Konno & Mead, 1967). In order to use absolute units of volume, the signal has to be calibrated with a spirometer. RIP has been used in a wide range of studies, from respiratory markers of vocal health (Loudon, Lee, & Holcomb, 1988) to respiratory patterns

in singing (Sundberg & Thalén, 2015; Watson & Hixon, 1985) and speech production (Hixon, Goldman, & Mead, 1973; Hixon, Mead, & Goldman, 1976). In this paper, we introduce RespInPeace, a Python toolkit for working with RIP signals. It has been developed with particular emphasis on processing and analyzing respiratory data in spontaneous, conversational speech (Włodarczak & Heldner, 2016, 2017, 2018).

RespInPeace overview

The respiratory signal is implemented as a single Python class, RIP. Additionally, a TimeIndexer class is implemented to allow easy access to respiratory samples by time stamps (or time stamp ranges) rather than by sample number. Internally, the respiratory signal is stored as a one-dimensional Numpy array, allowing for fast vectorized operations and for compatibility with the rest of the Python-based scientific computing ecosystem. All annotations (speech and respiratory segments) are stored as IntervalTiers (from the TextGridTools package, Buschmeier & Włodarczak, 2013).

Data input

RIP objects can be created directly from Numpy arrays and, optionally, IntervalTiers storing speech and breathing annotations. In addition, methods are implemented for reading respiratory data stored in WAV and comma-separated plain-text files. At the moment, a RIP object can only store a single respiratory channel. This will most commonly correspond to the summed signal from the two belts.

Figure 1. Respiratory signal before (left) and after (right) detrending.

Drift removal

Internally, detrending methods use the `detrend` function from `scipy.signal`. Two methods are available: *constant*, which removes the mean of the signal, and *linear*, which subtracts a least-squares fit. In addition to simple detrending methods, `RespInPeace` implements a mean 0.2 Hz mean filter for removing low-frequency periodic oscillations in the respiratory signal (Noto, Zhou, Schuele, Templer, & Zelano, 2018). An example of the raw and the detrended signal is presented in Figure 1.

Furthermore, a simple Butterworth IIR low-pass filter is included. Should a user require more complex filters, they can be designed using the standard `scipy.signal` tools.

Signal calibration

By default, the bottom and the top of speaker’s respiratory range is estimated as the 5th and 95th percentiles of the peak and trough values (see Figure 2). Note that this is different from the usual measures of vital lung capacity, which corresponds to the maximum volume of air exhaled following a maximum inhalation. Rather, this measure is designed to capture the respiratory range used in regular conversational speech. However, the signal can also be calibrated in terms of the vital capacity given that a vital capacity maneuver has been performed and marked in the input annotations.

In addition, given that inhalations are most commonly started around the

resting expiratory level (REL), the value of the latter is estimated as the median level of all trough values. However, since REL is rather sensitive to posture shifts, an alternative dynamic estimation method is also implemented, whereby REL value for each cycle is determined by calculating the median trough level within a preceding interval of specified duration. This method allows REL to move around within the respiratory range.

Figure 2. Respiratory signal with the respiratory range overlaid.

Signal segmentation

Given a large variability in respiratory patterns found in conversational speech, peak detection methods based on maximum velocity used in other studies of respiration (e.g. Rochet-Capellan & Fuchs, 2014) were found inadequate. Instead, a simpler method was used. Namely, the signal is first *z*-score normalized using a rolling window with the default length of 60 s. Subsequently, inhalatory and exhalatory segments are identified by locating peaks and troughs

in the normalized signal separated by at least one standard deviation (see Figure 3).

This method was found to work well even on spontaneous data: a manual check of the automatic boundaries in nine 20-minute three-party conversations resulted in adjustment of 12.6% of boundaries.

Figure 3. Respiratory signal with automatically detected peaks and troughs.

Figure 4. An example of a respiratory hold.

Breath hold detection

Breath holds are detected following the method proposed by Noto et al. (2018). Briefly, it consists in locating sharp peaks in a histogram of sample values within a respiratory cycle. The implementation in RespInPeace has been adapted to RIP signal (the original was proposed for airflow recordings) and for the characteristics of conversational speech breathing with a large variation in cycle durations and the possibility of a respiratory hold at any point within the exhalation. An example of a respiratory hold identified using this method is presented in Figure 4.

Signal parametrisation

RespInPeace implements methods for calculating the most common respiratory indices, such as slope and volumes. If the user is interested in extracting additional parameters, they are straightforward to calculate using the standard Python methods.

Closing remarks

In this paper, we presented the most fundamental features of RespInPeace. For more code examples, see a Jupyter notebook distributed as part of the RespInPeace repository. RespInPeace is released under the terms of the GNU General Public Licence version 3 (or later) and hosted on GitHub, thus encouraging community contributions.

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